

An arachnological excursion to the granitic Seychelles, 1-26th
January 1999.

Arachnid species lists for Silhouette, Cousine & Mahé

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These species lists accompany the account of arachnological collecting in Seychelles in:

Saaristo, M. 1999 - An arachnological excursion to the granitic Seychelles, 1-26th January 1999. *Phelsuma* 7; 62-64.

List of the Silhouette spiders

- = recorded from Silhouette, not collected during this excursion

+ = recorded from Silhouette, collected during this excursion

* = new to Silhouette, collected during this excursion

= new to Silhouette and the granitic Seychelles, collected during this excursion

% = new to Silhouette, collected by Dr. Gerlach between 1993-98, not during this excursion

Suborder MYGALOMORPHA

Family BARYCHELIDAE Simon, 1889

Sason Simon, 1898

% *S. seychellianum* Simon, 1898.

Family THERAPHOSIDAE

Chaetopelma Ausserer, 1871

- *C. gardineri* Hirst, 1911.

INCERTAE SEDIS

Genus ign. + Gen. sp. ign. (? = *Chonothele* sp. by Hirst 1911)

Suborder ARANEOMORPHA

Family FILISTATIDAE Ausserer, 1867

Pritha Lehtinen, 1967

* *P. heikkii* Saaristo, 1978

Family SCYTODIDAE Blackwall, 1864

"*Scytodes*"

% "*S.*" *pholcoides* Simon, 1898

* "*S.*" *fusca* (Walckenaer, 1837)

Soeuria Saaristo, 1997

* *Soeuria soeur* Saaristo, 1997

Family OCHYROCERATIDAE Fage, 1912

Theotima Simon, 1893

* *T. minutissima* (Petrunkevitch, 1929)

Ouette Saaristo, 1998

- *O. ouette* Saaristo, 1998

Speocera (*Complicera*) Berland, 1914

S. (C.) javana (Simon, 1905)

Genus ign.

Gen. sp. ign.

Family PHOLCIDAE C. L. Koch, 1851

Pholcus Walckenaer, 1805

P. sp. ign.

Micropholcus Deeleman-Reinhold & Prinsen, 1987

M. fauroti (Simon, 1887)

Artema Walckenaer, 1833

* *A. atlanta* Walckenaer, 1833

Physocyclus Simon, 1893

P. globosus (Taczanowski, 1874)

"*Holocnemus*"

+ "*H.*" *culiculus* Simon, 1898

"*H.*" sp. ign.

Smeringopus Simon, 1890

+ *S. pallidus* (Blackwall, 1858)

Modisimus Simon, 1893

M. culicinus (Simon, 1893)

Spermophorides Wunderlich, 1991

S. sp. ign.

Family TETRABLEMMIDAE O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1873

Mariblemma Lehtinen, 1981

+ *M. pandari* (Brignoli, 1978)

Tetrablemma O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1873

+ *T. benoiti* (Brignoli, 1978)

Family OONOPIIDAE Simon, 1890

Gamasomorpha Karsh, 1881

+ *G. mornensis* Benoit, 1979

* *G. insularis* Simon, 1907

* "*G.*" *david* Benoit, 1979

* "*G.*" *ladiguei* Benoit, 1979

% "*G.*" *sechellensis* Benoit, 1975

* "*G.*" *trichinalis* Benoit, 1979

Diblemma O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1908

D. donisthorpii O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1908

Silhouettella Benoit, 1979

+ *S. curieusei* Benoit, 1979

* *S. mahei* Benoit, 1979

Lionneta Benoit, 1979

L. sp. ign.

+ *L. sechellensis* Benoit, 1979

- *L. silhouettei* Benoit, 1979

Opopaea Simon, 1891

- *O. silhouettei* (Benoit, 1975)

Brignolia Dumitrescu & Georgesco, 1983

B. cubana Dumitrescu & Georgesco, 1983

Ischnothyreus Simon, 1892

* *I. pelifer* (Simon, 1891) = *I. sechellorum* Benoit, 1979 n. syn.

I. velox Jackson, 1908

Oonops Templeton

- *O. savyi* Benoit, 1979

Heteroonops Dalmas, 1916

* *H. spinimanus* (Simon, 1891)

Oonopinus Simon

* *O. kilikus* Suman, 1965 = *O. lodoiceaphilus* Benoit, 1979 n. syn.

Stenoonops Simon, 1891

- *S. opistornatus* Benoit, 1979

Orchestina

O. sp. ign.

Genus ign. 1

Sp. ign.

Family PALPIMANIDAE Thorell, 1870

Hybosida Simon, 1898

+ *H. dauban* Platnick, 1979

Steriphropus Simon, 1887

* *S. lacertosus* Simon, 1898

Family OECOBIDAE Blackwall, 1862

Maireja Lehtinen, 1967

* *M. marathaus* (Tikader, 1962)

Tarapuca Lehtinen, 1967

T. concinnus (Simon, 1892) n. comb.

Family ULOBORIDAE Thorell, 1869

Uloborus Latreille, 1806

+ *U. plumipes* Lucas, 1846

Zosis Walckenaer, 1841

+ *Z. gemiculatus* (Oliver, 1789)

Family MIMETIDAE Simon, 1881

Mimetus Hentz, 1832

Mimetus ign.

Family THERIDIIDAE Sundevall, 1833

Dipoena Thorell, 1869

* *D. spunkana* Roberts, 1978

Argyrodes Simon, 1864

+ *A. rostratus* Blackwall, 1877

+ *A. cognatus* (Blackwall, 1877)

* *A. fissifrontella* Saaristo, 1978

A. barycephalus Roberts, 1983

* *A. pusillus* Saaristo, 1978

- *A. recurvatus* Saaristo, 1978

Episinus Walckenaer, 1809

- *E. coecervus* Roberts, 1978

Theridion Walckenaer, 1805

T. scorinum Roberts, 1983

+ "*T.*" *libunum* Roberts, 1978

* "*T.*" *braueri* Simon, 1898 = *T. purifum* Roberts, 1978 n. syn.

* "*T.*" *clabnum* Roberts, 1978

Coleosoma O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1882

* *C. blanchum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1882

+ *C. floridanum* (Banks, 1900)

* *C. adamsoni* (Berland, 1935)

Anelosimus Simon, 1891

* *A. placens* (Keyserling, 1884)

Genus ign.

G. sp. ign.

Family THERIDIOSOMATIDAE

Zoma Saaristo, 1996

- *Z. zoma* Saaristo, 1996

- Andasta* Saaristo, 1996
 + *A. silte* Saaristo, 1996
- Family SYMPHYTOGNATHIDAE Hickman, 1931
Anapistula Gertsch, 1941
 - *A. seychellensis* Saaristo, 1996
Patu Marples, 1951
 + *P. silho* Saaristo, 1996
- Family MYSMENIDAE
Microdipoena Banks, 1895
 + *M. elsaе* Saaristo, 1978
- Family LINYPHIDAE Blackwall, 1859
Microbathyphantes van Helsdingen, 1988
 * *M. speciani* (Locket, 1968)
Nesoneta Millidge, 1991
 + *N. benoitia* (van Helsdingen, 1978)
Theoa Saaristo, 1995
 * *T. tricandata* (Locket, 1982)
Neonesiotes Millidge, 1991
 # *N. remiformis* Millidge, 1991
- Family TETRAGNATHIDAE Menge, 1866
Nephila Leach, 1815
 + *N. inaurata* (Walckenaer, 1841)
Nephilengys L. Koch, 1872
 + *N. cruentata* (Fabricius, 1775)
 "Leucauge"
 + "*L.*" *argyrescens* Benoit, 1978
 * "*L.*" *thorellii* (Blackwall, 1877)
 + "*L.*" *mornensis* Benoit, 1978
Tetragnatha Latreille, 1804
 * *T. mandibulata* Walckenaer, 1841
 * *T. marginata* (Thorell, 1890)
 + *T. modesta* Hirst, 1911
 + *T. nigricularis* Simon, 1897
- Family ARANEIDAE
Cyrtophora Simon, 1864
 + *C. citricola* (Forskol, 1775)
Arachnura Vinson, 1863
 - *A. scorpionoides* Vinson, 1863
Cyclosa Menge, 1866
 + *C. kibonotensis* Tullgren, 1910
 * *C. insulana* (Costa, 1834)
Drexelia McCook, 1892
 * *D. bifida* (Tullgren, 1910)
Prasonica Simon, 1895
 + *P. serjata* (Simon, 1895)
Neoscona Simon, 1864
 * *N. triangula* (Keyserling, 1864)
 * *N. subfusca* (C. L. Koch, 1837)
 - *N. morelii* (Vinson, 1863)
- Family LYCOSIDAE Sundevall, 1833
Trochosa C. L. Koch, 1848
 * *T. urbana* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1878)
Bristowiella Saaristo, 1980
 * *B. seychellensis* (Bristowe, 1973)
- Family OXYOPIDAE Thorell, 1870
Oxyopes Latreille, 1804
 + *O. dumonii* (Vinson, 1863)
- Family MITURGIDAE Lehtinen, 1967
 Genus ign.
 # Gen. sp. ign.
- Family CLUBIONIDAE Wagner 1887
Clubiona Latreille, 1804

- + *C. mahensis* Simon, 1893
 # *C. sp. ign.*
 + "*C.*" *nigromaculosa* Blackwall, 1877
- Family CORINNIDAE** Karsch, 1880
Oedignatha Thorell, 1881 * *O. scrobiculata* Thorell, 1881
 Genus ign. 1. # Gen. sp. ign.
 Genus ign. 2. # Gen. sp. ign.
- Family CRYPTOHELIDAE** L. Koch, 1872
Cryptothela L. Koch, 1872 + *C. albanidi* Simon, 1893
- Family GNAPHOSIDAE** Banks, 1892
Camillina Berland, 1919 * *C. cordifera* (Tullgren, 1910)
Xerophaeus Purcell, 1907 # *X. sp. ign.*
- Family SELENOPIDAE** Simon, 1897
Selenops Dufour, 1817 + *S. secretus* Hirst, 1911
- Family HETEROPODIDAE** Thorell, 1874
Heteropoda Latreille, 1804 * *H. venatoria* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Rhitymna Simon, 1897 + *R. valida* (Blackwall, 1877)
Rhacocnemis Simon, 1898 - *R. guttata* (Blackwall, 1877)
Thomasettia Hirst, 1911 - *T. seychelliana* Hirst, 1911
- Family THOMISIDAE** Sundevall, 1833
 "Thomisus"
 + "*T.*" *stenningi* Pocock, 1900 [= *T. citrinellus* auct. nec Simon, 1875]
- Family SALTICIDAE** Blackwall, 1841
Goleba Wanless, 1980
 + *G. pollens* (Blackwall, 1877)
Sadies Wanless, 1984
 + *S. gibbosa* Wanless, 1984
 * *S. seychellensis* Wanless, 1984
Myrmarachne MacLeay, 1838
 + *M. constricta* (Blackwall, 1877)
Baviola Simon, 1898
 - *B. braueri* Simon, 1898
 - *B. luteosignata* Wanless, 1984
 + *B. spatulata* Wanless, 1984
 + *B. vannolli* Wanless, 1894
Hispo Simon, 1885
 - *H. alboclypea* Wanless, 1984
Hasarius Simon, 1871
 * *H. adamsonii* (Savigny & Audouin, 1825)
 + *H. rufociliatus* Simon, 1898
Hyllus C. L. Koch, 1846
 + *H. acutus* (Blackwall, 1877)
Carrhotus Thorell, 1891
 + *C. belus* Wanless, 1984
Plexippus C. L. Koch, 1846
 * *P. paykullii* (Savigny & Audouin, 1825)
Salpesia Simon, 1901
 * *S. soricina* Simon, 1901
Heliophanus C. L. Koch, 1833
 + *H. activus* (Blackwall, 1877)
Menemerus Simon, 1868
 * *M. bivittatus* (Dufour, 1831)

List of the Cousine spiders

- = send by Mr. Hitchins or Ms La Maitre, not collected during this excursion
 + = send by Mr. Hitchins or Ms La Maitre, collected also during this excursion
 * = new to Cousine
 # = new also to the granitic Seychelles

Family SCYTODIDAE Blackwall, 1864**"Scytodes"**+ "*S.*" *fusca* (Walckenaer, 1837)*Soeuria* Saaristo, 1997* *S. soeur* Saaristo, 1997**Family OCHYRO CERATIDAE** Fage, 1912*Theotima* Simon, 1893+ *T. minutissima* (Petrunkevitch, 1929)**Family PHOLCIDAE** C. L. Koch, 1851*Micropholcus* Doeleman-Reinhold & Prinsen, 1987* *M. favroti* (Simon, 1887)*Physocyclus* Simon, 1893* *P. globosus* (Taczanowski, 1874)*Smeringopus* Simon, 1890+ *S. pallidus* (Blackwall, 1858)*Modisimus* Simon, 1893* *M. culicinus* (Simon, 1893)**Family OONOPIDAE** Simon, 1890*Gamasomorpha* Karsh, 1881* "*G.*" *ladiguei* Benoit, 1979* "*G.*" *trichinalis* Benoit, 1979*Silhouettella* Benoit, 1979* *S. mahei* Benoit, 1979*Brignolia* Dumitresco & Georgesco, 1983* *B. cubana* Dumitresco & Georgesco, 1983*Ischnothyreus* Simon, 1892* *I. peltifer* (Simon, 1891) = *I. sechellorum* Benoit, 1979 n. syn.* *I. velox* Jackson, 1908*Oonopinus* Simon* *O. kilikus* Suman, 1965 = *O. lodoiceaphilus* Benoit, 1979 n. syn.**Genus ign 2.**

Sp. ign.

Family OECOBIDAE Blackwall, 1862*Maitreja* Lehtinen, 1967* *M. marathaus* (Tikader, 1962)*Tarapaca* Lehtinen, 1967+ *T. concinnus* (Simon, 1892) n. comb.**Family THERIDIIDAE** Sundevall, 1833*Theridion* Walckenaer, 1805* "*T.*" *ciabnum* Roberts, 1978*Coleosoma* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1882* *C. floridanum* (Banks, 1900)* *C. adamsani* (Berland, 1935)**Family MYSMENIDAE***Microdipoena* Banks, 1895* *M. elscæ* Saaristo, 1978**Family LINYPHIIDAE** Blackwall, 1859*Nesioneta* Millidge, 1991* *N. benoitia* (van Helsdingen, 1978)*Theoa* Saaristo, 1995* *T. tricaudata* (Locket, 1982)*Neonesiotes* Millidge, 1991* *N. remiformis* Millidge, 1991

- Family TETRAGNATHIDAE** Menge, 1866
Nephila Leach, 1815
 - *N. maurata* (Walckenaer, 1841)
Tetragnatha Latreille, 1804
 * *T. marginata*
- Family ARANEIDAE**
Drexelia McCook, 1892
 + *D. bifida* (Tullgren, 1910)
- Family LYCOSIDAE** Sundevall, 1833
Trochosa C. L. Koch, 1848
 * *T. urbana* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1878)
Bristowiella Saaristo, 1980
 - *B. seychellenstris* (Bristowe, 1973)
- Family CLUBIONIDAE** Wagner 1887
Clubiona Latreille, 1804
 + *C. sp. ign.*
- Family CORINNIDAE** Karsch, 1880
Oedignatha Thorell, 1881
 * *O. scrobiculata* Thorell, 1881
- Genus ign. 1.**
 * Gen. sp. ign.
- Genus ign. 2.**
 + Gen. sp. ign.
- Family CRYPTYTHELIDAE** L. Koch, 1872
Cryptothele L. Koch, 1872
 * *C. alluandi* Simon, 1893
- Family PRODIDOMIDAE** Simon, 1884
Genus ign.
 # G. sp. ign.
- Family GNAPHOSIDAE** Banks, 1892
Camillina Berland, 1919
 + *C. cordifera* (Tullgren, 1910)
Xerophaeus Purcell, 1907
 - *X. espoir* Platnick, 1981
 * *X. sp. ign.*
- Family SELENOPIDAE** Simon, 1897
Selenops Dufour, 1817
 + *S. secretus* Hirst, 1911
- Family HETEROPODIDAE** Thorell, 1874
Heteropoda Latreille, 1804
 + *H. venatoria* (Linnaeus, 1758)
- Family SALTICIDAE** Blackwall, 1841
Hasarius Simon, 1871
 + *H. adansonii* (Savigny & Audouin, 1825)
Hyllus C. L. Koch, 1846
 - *H. acutus* (Blackwall, 1877)
Plexippus C. L. Koch, 1846
 - *P. paykullii* (Savigny & Audouin, 1825)
Heliophanus C. L. Koch, 1833
 + *H. activus* (Blackwall, 1877)
Menemerus Simon, 1868
 - *M. bivittatus* (Dufour, 1831)
Harmochirus
 * *H. sp. ign.*

List of the spiders of Mahé

Suborder MYGALOMORPHA

- Family BARYCHELIDAE** Simon, 1889
Sason Simon, 1887
 - *S. sechellianum* Simon, 1898
- Family THERAPHOSIDAE** Thorell, 1870
Chaetopelma Ausserer, 1871
 - *C. gardneri* Hirst, 1911

Suborder ARANEOMORPHA

Family FILISTATIDAE Ausserer, 1867

Prüha Lehtinen, 1967 + *P. garciai* (Simon, 1892)

Family SCYTODIDAE Blackwall, 1864

"*Scytodes*"
- "*S.*" *berthelotii* (Lucas, 1839)
- "*S.*" *fusca* (Walckenaer, 1837)
- "*S.*" *pholcoides* (Simon, 1898)
- "*S.*" *velutina* (Lowe, 1835)

Family TELEMIDAE Fage, 1913

Seychellia Saaristo, 1978 + *S. wiljoi* Saaristo, 1978

Family OCHYRO CERATIDAE Fage, 1912

Thoetina Simon, 1893 + *T. minutissima* (Petrunkevitch, 1929)
Genus ign. * Gen. sp. ign.

Family PHOLCIDAE C. L. Koch, 1851

Pholcus Walckenaer, 1805

* *P.* sp. ign.

Micropholcus Döeleman-Reinhold & Prinsen, 1987

* *M. fauroti* (Simon, 1887)

Artema Walckenaer, 1833

- *A. atlanta* Walckenaer, 1833

"*Holocnemus*"

+ "*H.*" *culiculus* Simon, 1898

Smeringopus Simon, 1890

+ *S. pallidus* (Blackwall, 1858)

Modisimus Simon, 1893

* *M. culicinus* (Simon, 1893)

Family TETRABLEMMIDAE O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1873

Tetrablemma O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1873 + *T. benoiti* (Brignoli, 1978)

Family SEGESTRIIDAE Simon, 1893

Ariadna Savigny & Audouin, 1825

+ *A. ustulata* Simon, 1898

Family OONOPIDAE Simon, 1890

Gamasomorpha Karsh, 1881

- *G. mormensis* Benoit, 1979

- *G. insularis* Simon, 1907

- *G. austera* Simon, 1898

- "*G.*" *david* Benoit, 1979

+ "*G.*" *ladiguet* Benoit, 1979

- "*G.*" *sechellensis* Benoit, 1975

- "*G.*" *silhouettei* Benoit, 1979

- "*G.*" *trichinalis* Benoit, 1979

Silhouettella Benoit, 1979

- *S. mahei* Benoit, 1979

Lionneta Benoit, 1979

- *L. mahensis* Benoit, 1979

+ *L. sechellensis* Benoit, 1979

Ischnothyreus Simon, 1892

- *I. jivani* Benoit, 1979

- *I. orophilus* Benoit, 1979

- *I. peltifer* (Simon, 1891) = *I. sechellorum* Benoit, 1979 n. syn.

I. sp. ign.

Oonops Templeton

- *O. savyi* Benoit, 1979

Heteroonops Dalmas, 1916

- *H. spinimanus* (Simon, 1891)

- Orchestina*
 - *O. sechellorum* Benoit, 1979
 * *O.* sp. ign.
- Family PALPIMANIDAE** Thorell, 1870
Hybosida Simon, 1898
 - *H. lucida* Simon, 1898
Steriphropus Simon, 1887
 - *S. lacertosus* Simon, 1898
- Family OECOBIDAE** Blackwall, 1862
Maitreja Lehtinen, 1967
 - *M. marathaus* (Tikader, 1962)
Tarapaca Lehtinen, 1967
 * *T. concinnus* (Simon, 1892) n. comb.
- Family ULOBORIDAE** Thorell, 1869
Uloborus Latreille, 1806
 + *U. plumipes* Lucas, 1846
 - *U.* sp. 2. sensu Saaristo 1978
Zosis Walckenaer, 1841
 + *Z. geniculatus* (Oliver, 1789)
- Family THERIDIIDAE** Sundevall, 1833
Argyrodes Simon, 1864
 + *A. argyrodes* (Walckenaer, 1837)
 + *A. rostratus* Blackwall, 1877
 + *A. cognatus* (Blackwall, 1877)
 + *A. fissifrontella* Saaristo, 1978
 + *A. pusillus* Saaristo, 1978
 - *A. recurvatus* Saaristo, 1978
Episinus Walckenaer, 1809
 - *E. coecervus* Roberts, 1978
Theridion Walckenaer, 1805
 + "*T.*" *braueri* (Simon, 1898)
 + "*T.*" *clabnum* Roberts, 1978
 + "*T.*" *libanum* Roberts, 1978
Coleosoma O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1882
 - *C. blandum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1882
 + *C. floridana* (Banks, 1900)
 + *C. adamsoni* (Berland, 1935)
 "*Achearenea*"
 - "*A.*" *tepidarioria* (C. L. Koch, 1841)
 - "*A.*" *mudula* (L. Koch, 1872)
Anelosimus Simon, 1891
 - *A. placens* (Keyserling, 1884)
- Family THERIDIOSOMATIDAE** Simon, 1881
Andasta Saaristo, 1996
 - *A. benoiti* (Roberts, 1978)
- Family MYSMENIDAE** Petrunkevitch, 1928
Microdipoena Banks, 1895
 - *M. elsaе* Saaristo, 1978
- Family LINYPHIDAE** Blackwall, 1859
Microbathyphantes van Helsdingen, 1988
 - *M. palmarius* (Murples, 1955)
Nesioneta Millidge, 1991
 - *N. benoiti* (van Helsdingen, 1978)
Thoa Saaristo, 1995
 + *T. tricaudata* (Locket, 1982)
Neonesiotes Millidge, 1991
 * *N. remiformis* Millidge, 1991
- Family TETRAGNATHIDAE** Menge, 1866
Nephila Leach, 1815
 + *N. inaurata* (Walckenaer, 1841)
Nephilengys L. Koch, 1872
 + *N. cruentata* (Fabricius, 1775)

"Leucauge"

- + "*L.*" *argyrescens* Benoit, 1978
- + "*L.*" *thorellii* (Blackwall, 1877)
- "*L.*" *mornensis* Benoit, 1978

***Tetragnatha* Latreille, 1804**

- + *T. mandibulata* Walckenaer, 1842
- *T. foliifera* Simon, 1879
- *T. marginata* (Thorell, 1890)
- + *T. nigricularis* Simon, 1897

Family ARANEIDAE Latreille, 1806***Argiope* Savigny & Audouin, 1825**

- *A. anasuja* (Thorell, 1887)

***Cyrtophora* Simon, 1864**

- + *C. citricola* (Forskol, 1775)

***Cyclosa* Menge, 1866**

- *C. insulana* (Costa, 1834)

***Drexelia* McCook, 1892**

- * *D. bifida* (Tullgren, 1910)

***Prasonica* Simon, 1895**

- *P. seriata* (Simon, 1895)

***Kilima* Grasshoff, 1970**

- *K. decens* (Blackwall, 1866)

***Neoscona* Simon, 1864**

- *N. morelii* (Vinson, 1863)
- *N. punctigera* (Doleschall, 1857)
- *N. subfusca* (C. L. Koch, 1837)
- + *N. triangula* (Keyserling, 1864)

***Gasteracantha* Latreille, 1831**

- * *G. brevispina* (Doleschall, 1857)

Family LYCOSIDAE Sundevall, 1833***Trochosa* C. L. Koch, 1848**

- + *T. urbana* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1878)

***Bristowiella* Saaristo, 1980**

- + *B. seychellensis* (Bristowe, 1973)

Family PISAURIDAE Simon, 1890***Voraptus* Simon, 1898**

- *V. tenellus* (Simon, 1893)

Family OXYOPIIDAE Thorell, 1870***Oxyopes* Latreille, 1804**

- *O. dumonti* (Vinson, 1863)

***Peucezia* Thorell, 1869**

- *P. pulchra* (Blackwall, 1865)

Family CLUBIONIDAE Wagner 1887**"*Clubiona*"**

- "*C.*" *mahensis* Simon, 1893
- "*C.*" *nigrimaculosa* Blackwall, 1877

Family CORINNIDAE Karsch, 1880***Oedignatha* Thorell, 1881**

- + *O. scrobiculata* Thorell, 1881

Genus ign.

- * *G. sp. ign.*

Family CRYPTOHELIDAE L. Koch, 1872***Cryptothele* L. Koch, 1872**

- + *C. alluaudi* Simon, 1893

Family GNAPHOSIDAE Banks, 1892***Microdrassus* Dalman, 1920**

- *M. incudax* (Simon, 1898)

***Camillina* Berland, 1919**

- *C. cordifera* (Tullgren, 1910)

***Xerophaeus* Purcell, 1907**

- *X. espoir* Platnick, 1981

- Family CTENIDAE** Keyserling, 1877
Apolonia Simon, 1898
 - *A. segmentata* Simon, 1898
- Family SELENOPIIDAE** Simon, 1897
Selenops Dufour, 1817
 - *S. secretus* Hirst, 1911
- Family HETEROPODIDAE** Thorell, 1874
Heteropoda Latreille, 1804
 - *H. venatoria* (Jinnaeus, 1758)
Rhitymna Simon, 1897
 + *R. valida* (Blackwall, 1877)
Sparssus Walckenaer, 1805
 - *S. walckenaeri* (Savigny & Audouin, 1825)
Rhacocnemis Simon, 1898
 - *R. guttata* (Blackwall, 1877)
Thomasettia Hirst, 1911
 - *T. seychellana* Hirst, 1911
Pleurotus Simon, 1898
 - *P. braueri* Simon, 1898
Stipax Simon, 1898
 - *S. triangulifer* Simon, 1898
- Family THOMISIDAE** Sundevall, 1833
 "Firmicus"
 - *F. insularis* Blackwall, 1877
 "Thomisus"
 + "T." *stenningi* Pocock, 1900
- Family SALTICIDAE** Blackwall, 1841
Goleba Wanless, 1980
 - *G. pallens* (Blackwall, 1877)
Sadies Wanless, 1984
 + *S. fulgida* Wanless, 1984
 * *S. gibbosa* Wanless, 1984
 - *S. seychellensis* Wanless, 1984
 - *S. trifasciata* Wanless, 1984
Baviola Simon, 1898
 - *B. braueri* Simon, 1898
 - *B. luteosignata* Wanless, 1984
 * *B. spatulata* Wanless, 1984
 + *B. vannoli* Wanless, 1894
Myrmarachne MacLeay, 1838
 + *M. constricta* (Blackwall, 1877)
Cynapes Simon, 1900
 - *C. wrightii* (Blackwall, 1877)
Hispa Simon, 1885
 - *H. alboclypea* Wanless, 1984
 + *H. striolata* Simon, 1898
Hasarius Simon, 1871
 - *H. adamsonii* (Savigny & Audouin, 1825)
 - *H. mahensis* Wanless, 1984
 + *H. rufociliatus* Simon, 1898
Hyllus C. L. Koch, 1846
 + *H. acutus* (Blackwall, 1877)
Carrhotus Thorell, 1891
 - *C. bellus* Wanless, 1984
Plexippus C. L. Koch, 1846
 + *P. paykullii* (Savigny & Audouin, 1825)
Heliophanus C. L. Koch, 1833
 - *H. activus* (Blackwall, 1877)
Pseudicius Simon, 1885
 - *P. seychellensis* Wanless, 1984
Menemerus Simon, 1868
 + *M. bivittatus* (Dufour, 1831)

Harmochirus Simon, 1885

• *H. n.* sp.

Genus ign. # Ci. sp. ign.

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